

DAMAGE TO THE INSULATION OF POWER SUPPLY CABLES OF NON-PULLING CONSUMERS

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Abstract The article provides general information on the main causes of damage to power supply cables of non-traction consumers of railways and determines the dependence of cable serviceability on the nature of the insulating sheath and protective metal elements of the cable.

Keywords: polyethylene shell, insulation, electrical energy, contact network, affected line, voltage, aluminum shell, electric and magnetic field effects

One of the main causes of damage to power supply cables of non-tractor railway consumers is the damage of the insulation shell and the erosion of the metal protective element under the conditions of use. As a result, the resistance of the cable insulation decreases and the normal operation of the cable line is disturbed. The serviceability of the cable is determined by the nature of the insulating sheath and the dependence on the protective metal elements of the cable.

Cables of the MP-1, MP-3 and MP-5 brands up to 35 kV are produced with oil-soaked paper insulation. Nowadays, these cables are being replaced by polymer insulated cables. A polyethylene sheath is used for underground cables.

Below are the advantages of polyethylene insulated cables compared to paper-oil insulated cables:

- a) drying of the insulation at the highest point is observed when the ground burial heights of paper-oil insulated cables are different. Cables with polyethylene insulation do not have this drawback;
- b) special materials and devices are not required for the installation of cables with polyethylene insulation. For example, it is not necessary to wrap a paper tape soaked in oil at the joint;
- c) polyethylene insulated cables have small values of the coefficient of dielectric dissipation angle and relative dielectric absorbance;
- d) additional heating is not required when burying polyethylene cables in the ground (but cables with a voltage of up to 30 kV can be buried at a temperature of minus 200C);
- e) polyethylene shell is less sensitive to environmental changes;
- f) cables with polyethylene insulation are resistant to vibration.

Polyethylene insulated cables have several advantages as well as disadvantages. The process of electrical wear and the appearance of the tracking channel depends on the purity of the insulation material and the hermeticity along the length of the cable. Losses in the transmission of electrical energy occur mainly due to dielectric loss. The service life of the cables is evaluated by the flatness of the surface of the part between the screen and the insulation shell. In some parts of the cable, micro-heights are formed during production, and as a result, the value of the electric field strength increases. In order to maintain the performance of polyethylene-insulated cables, it is necessary to prevent the ingress of moisture through the insulating material to the current-carrying parts of the cable. Currently, lead, aluminum and polymer materials are used as cable sheath material. The least absorbent of these materials is lead. It has a serious drawback: it is an expensive and rare material, it corrodes quickly under the influence of electric currents and has a large weight.

The plastic shell is cheap, but it has great moisture absorption compared to the lead shell, and the electrical parameters are also relatively low. Aluminum

material is the most convenient to use. But this material is also prone to corrosion. Therefore, rubber hoses are used as its shell, and the resistance of the insulating material should not be less than 5 MΩ·km. The risk of corrosion of the aluminum sheath occurs as a result of damage to the insulating hose when moving cables from one place to another, during use or during installation. Signaling, centralization and blocking devices, stations and administrative buildings are cut off from power supply when power supply cables of non-traction consumers of railways are damaged. In order to reduce damage to the power supply system of non-pulling consumers, it is advisable to use modern cables with increased insulation strength.

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